

Effect of Simplified Worksheets Approach in Mathematical Skills of Grade 4 Learners

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Abstract. This study aimed to assess the impact of a worksheet approach on the mathematical skills of Grade Four learners at Almendras Elementary School. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design, the research investigated a sample of 76 students. Section A (n=38) served as the control group, while Section B (n=38) served as the experimental group. The study was conducted at Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur, focusing on an intact group of learners with homogeneous academic performance. Non-random assignment was used to ensure all participants from both sections A and B were included. The findings indicate that the implementation of simplified worksheets significantly enhanced the mathematical skills of Grade Four learners. Statistical analysis revealed a notable difference in post-test scores between the control and experimental groups, suggesting the efficacy of the worksheet approach in improving student outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. simplified . 2. worksheets . 3. mathematical skills.

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1. Introduction

In schools worldwide, Mathematics holds a pivotal role, yet many students in the Philippines encounter significant barriers hindering their full participation and success in the subject. These challenges manifest in struggles with General Mathematics activities, impacting their comprehension and proficiency in fundamental operations (Program for International Student Assessment, 2019). The ability to solve mathematical problems is crucial for practical applications such as financial transactions and spatial measurements, underscoring the importance of honing basic math skills like addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division (Dass, 2014; Căprioară, 2015). Visual representations of numerical data through charts and graphs also play a critical role in understanding and communicating information effectively (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2009). Workbooks are valuable tools offering structured exercises and solutions to reinforce mathematical concepts, making them essential for targeted skill improvement (Johnson, 2009). Despite the universal recognition of Mathematics' importance in education, Philippine students continue to face obstacles, particularly evident in regions like the Division of Davao Del Sur, Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, where learners struggle with mastering basic operations (Yadav, 2017). The situa-

tion in these regions highlights a broader issue that requires immediate attention to ensure that all students have the opportunity to succeed in Mathematics. To address these challenges, innovative approaches such as the worksheet method have been proposed by educators like grade four teachers, aiming to enhance learning outcomes (Taplin, n.d.). The review of significant literature emphasizes the multifaceted factors influencing students' mathematical performance. These include learner-related, teacher-related, and family-related variables, all impacting academic achievement (Waters Marzano, 2016). For instance, socioeconomic status is a critical determinant of success, influencing access to resources and support systems. Cognitive and metacognitive behaviors, such as students' attitudes towards learning and their ability to regulate their learning processes, also play significant roles (Power, 2013). Furthermore, parental support is another crucial factor, as it can significantly affect students' motivation and engagement with Mathematics. Students in private versus public schools demonstrate varying motivational factors and parental influences that affect their mathematical proficiency (Abdullah et al., 2010). Private school students often benefit from more resources and parental involvement, which can lead to better educational outcomes. However, this disparity highlights the need for targeted interventions in public schools to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to excel in Mathematics. Effective teaching methods are pivotal in fostering mathematical competence, with problem-solving approaches gaining prominence for their ability to engage students actively and promote a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts (Yavuz Erbay, 2015). Problem-solving methodologies facilitate collaborative learning environments that encourage peer interaction and cooperative problem-solving skills (Gokkurt et al., 2012). Such approaches not only enhance mathematical abilities but also develop critical 21st-century skills

like collaboration and innovation (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2009). Research underscores the significance of instructional strategies that incorporate problem-solving tasks into the curriculum, supporting students in applying mathematical concepts to real-world scenarios (OECD, 2019). However, the effectiveness of these approaches varies across diverse student backgrounds and educational settings, necessitating tailored interventions for heterogeneous classrooms (Lester Cai, 2016). For example, students from different cultural backgrounds may have unique learning styles and preferences that need to be considered when designing instructional strategies. Theoretical frameworks by Hallam (2012) and Soo (2017) advocate for structured learning environments and teacher support to optimize student learning outcomes, reinforcing the importance of effective pedagogical practices (Lester Charles, 2003). These frameworks suggest that a well-organized classroom environment, combined with supportive teacher-student interactions, can significantly enhance students' engagement and learning in Mathematics. The current study contributes to this body of knowledge by examining the impact of the worksheet approach on enhancing mathematical skills among grade four learners at Almendras Elementary School, addressing critical gaps in research on instructional methodologies in mathematics education (Yavuz Erbay, 2015). By focusing on a specific educational context, this study provides insights into how targeted interventions can improve mathematical proficiency in challenging settings. In conclusion, while Mathematics remains universally recognized as fundamental to education, the challenges faced by Filipino students underscore the need for innovative instructional approaches. The worksheet approach, supported by collaborative learning and problem-solving strategies, emerges as a promising intervention to improve mathematical proficiency and foster essential 21st-century skills among learn-

ers (Capar Tarim, 2015). By addressing these challenges through targeted educational interventions, educators can empower students to succeed in Mathematics and beyond, bridging the gap in academic achievement and promoting lifelong learning. This synthesis draws upon diverse sources to illuminate the complexity of factors influencing mathematical performance, underscoring the importance of tailored educational strategies in enhancing student outcomes. It is crucial for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders to collaborate and implement effective instructional practices that cater to the diverse needs of students, ensuring that all learners have the opportunity to develop strong mathematical skills and achieve academic success.

In schools throughout the world, Mathematics is regarded as the most significant subject. Unfortunately, because of the multiple barriers that keep them from fully participating, many students in the Philippines find it difficult. Students have a tough time in solving activities in General Mathematics. From calculating financial transactions to measuring spaces and objects, math skills are an important part of everyday life. Improving your basic math skills can help you get a job, perform better in your current position, and make your personal life easier to manage. Basic math skills are those that involve making calculations of amounts, sizes, or other measurements. Core concepts like addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division provide a foundation for learning and using more advanced math concepts. Being proficient in basic math skills will help you both in the workplace and your daily life. Numbers are frequently presented in visual formats. A basic math skill to learn is how to read and understand charts and graphs. Being able to read the axes, trend line and data points will help you gain a deeper understanding of underlying data. It will also help you make graphs and charts to better illustrate your points. Math workbooks provide sample math problems to

solve and are a wonderful way to practice your basic math skills. Often, math workbooks will provide instructions and advice on how to complete the problems as well as answers so you can check your work. If there is a particular topic in math that you find challenging, look for a math workbook that focuses primarily on that math skill. Mathematics is well-known as universally important in schools globally. However, many students in the Philippines struggle with it due to the various obstacles that prevent them from fully engaging in it (Program for International Student Assessment, 2019). Despite the various reports and recommendations that have been produced regarding education in the country, it is widely acknowledged that Mathematics is regarded as one of the toughest subjects that students are taught in schools. In the Division of Davao Del Sur, particularly in Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, problem among learners in mathematics is prevalent. Learners have not mastered the four fundamental operations in mathematics. They find it difficult to comprehend simple mathematical problems. The researcher, being a grade four teacher, produces an innovation of introducing the worksheet approach which she hopes to address the problem. Hence, this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— Business leaders rely on data for decision-making, and presenting numerical findings effectively is crucial in the workplace. Many factors contribute to poor math performance, but this study aims to find sustainable solutions during the pandemic (Department of Education, 2019). The National Achievement Test (NAT) results show low proficiency in mathematics among Grade 12 students, highlighting the need for improved instructional materials and focus on classroom instruction.

Educators have long explored variables affecting academic achievement, including student, family, school, and peer factors (Waters Marzano, 2016). Mathematics is seen as chal-

lenging yet essential, requiring a strong foundation for practical application (Yadav, 2017). Socioeconomic conditions, non-cognitive and metacognitive behaviors affect math performance, with poor-performing students often lacking resources and motivation.

The 21st Century Learning Framework emphasizes skills like problem-solving and collaboration for success in a globalized society (Dass, 2014; Fong et al., 2014). Problem-solving is crucial in mathematics education, involving systematic approaches to understanding and solving problems (Allen Graden, 2002; Căprioară, 2015). Approaches promoting active participation and problem-solving in math have emerged, with teaching through problem-solving seen as effective (Yavuz Erbay, 2015; Taplin, n.d.).

The problem-solving approach enhances mathematical understanding and student engagement, fostering a collaborative learning environment (Cai Lester, 2010; SAIDE, 2008). Research shows that collaboration in problem-solving improves critical thinking, social interaction, and academic performance (Laal Ghodsi, 2012; Gokkurt et al., 2012). However, most studies focus on the implementation of problem-solving as a teaching method, rather than as an instructional intervention (Kuzle, 2018; Widada et al., 2019).

This study investigates the effects of the problem-solving approach on first-year college students' performance and attitudes in College Algebra, comparing it with traditional teaching methods. The intervention involved cooperative learning and problem-solving strategies, showing significant improvements in overall problem-solving and geometry (Johnson et al., 1993; Gillies, 2016). The cooperative learning approach promotes positive interdependence, individual accountability, and social skills, enhancing mathematical problem-solving in heterogeneous classrooms (Capar Tarim, 2015).

Mathematical problem-solving prepares stu-

dents for modern society, applying mathematical concepts in practical situations (Gravemeijer et al., 2017). Effective problem-solving instruction develops critical 21st-century skills necessary for academic and career success.

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed the methodologies used to solve the current issue. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also served as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—

This study was anchored on Hallam's (2012) theory, which posits that home learning is more effective for older students than for their younger counterparts. This is primarily because older students are better able to self-regulate their learning and have more background knowledge to draw upon. For similar reasons, high ability students typically benefit more from home learning than low ability students. Frequent home learning may result to establishment of good study habit. This was supported by Soo (2017) who expressed that teacher scaffolding is essential to guide effective home learning. Parental involvement is desirable, but it should not be essential, otherwise the nature of the task is too complex for successful completion. When the teacher gives homework to learners and regularly checks them, then, the learners can form good study habit. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of the study. The skills of teachers in lesson reinforcement will be the focus of this study. The effect on the utilization of worksheet on the mathematical skills of the grade four learners will be evaluated in terms of its effectiveness that will be determined through the study conducted by the researcher.

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—This study learners in Almendras Elementary School. Accordingly, in this study it sought to answer the aimed to determine the effect of worksheet approach on the mathematical skills of grade four following questions.

- (1) What are the pretest scores of the pre-school learners both controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What are the posttest scores of the pre-school learners in both controlled and experimental group?
- (3) Is there a significant difference between the post scores of the controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of Worksheet Approach on the letter sound recognition skills of pre-school learners?

1.5. *Null Hypothesis*—The null hypothesis in this study tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. There is no significant difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. H02. Worksheet Approach has no effect on the letter sound recognition skills of pre-school learners.

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The research findings provided insights and meaningful results to the following: School Heads. The outcome of this study can serve as a guide for best practices that grade four teachers can share and utilize to help their students develop mathematical skills. Once these skills were developed, the learners will be better prepared to advance

to higher levels of mathematics. Teachers. The results of this study would enable teachers to understand the struggles of learners in mathematics. Thus, it would give them a smart idea of developing intervention to address mathematical problems among early grades learners. Future Researchers. This study would be beneficial to future students who will be conducting similar studies. This can serve as their literature that would guide them during the study.

1.7. *Definition of Terms*—In this study, terms were defined conceptually and operationally to deepen understanding on the following terms: Claveria Reading Approach refers to the techniques which was used to develop the reading skills of the learners using text marking.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Locale and Sample—This study conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the seventy-six pre-school pupils – 38 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 38 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils
1 Section A	38
2 Section B	38
Total	76

2.2. Data Source and Analysis—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a superior design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

Design of the Study

The following statistical tools are used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean used to describe the mathematical skills of the grade four learners. Eta square is used to measure the magnitude of effect work-sheet approach on the mathematical skills of grade four learners. This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learn-

Fig. 2. Gantt Chart

ing where the teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher must meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance test consist of a 35 –item test that will eventually determine the reading skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all

subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be extremely helpful to assess the letter sound recognition skills of the pre-school learners. On the hand, a posttest will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the mathematical skills of the grade four learners, the following continuum is used based on DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.3. *Data Gathering and Processing*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the re-

searcher drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were

sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Del Sur, Dr. Nelson C. Lopez CESO V, and the school principal of Almendras Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts, preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Almendras Elementary School and after the research

questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade four learners. The controlled group got the mean of 19.24 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 20.43 or Beginning. It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs to Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Gokkurt et al. (2012) who stated that mathematics remains a challenge for most countries. For this reason, different approaches that promote students’ active participation in the teaching and learning process

have emerged. In recent years, using problem-solving in teaching mathematics subjects was one of the methods used in teaching the subject (Yavuz Erbay, 2015), and mathematics teachers have considered the shifting of emphasis from teaching problem-solving to teaching through problem-solving (Taplin, n.d.). It is believed that important mathematics concepts and procedures can be best taught through simplified worksheets that includes problem-solving tasks or activities, which engage students in thinking about the important mathematical concepts and skills they need to learn (South African Institute for Distance Education [SAIDE], 2008).

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Learners

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	38	19.24	54.97	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	38	20.43	58.37	Beginning

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade four learners. The controlled group got the mean of 28.17 or Beginning while the experimental group gained the mean of 29.97 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 9.54 from a mean rating of 20.43 to 29.97. This means that the experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Gokkurt et al. (2012) who stated that mathematics remains a challenge for most countries. For this reason, different approaches that promote students' active participation in the teaching and learning process have emerged. In recent years, using problem-solving in teaching mathematics subjects was one of the methods used in teaching the subject (Yavuz Erbay, 2015), and

mathematics teachers have considered the shifting of emphasis from teaching problem-solving to teaching through problem-solving (Taplin, n.d.). In the simplified worksheet approach using problem-solving approach, learning occurs during the process of attempting to solve problems, in which relevant mathematics concepts and skills are embedded. As students solve problems, they can use various approaches, utilize the knowledge that they have previously learned, and employ convincing strategies to justify their ideas. The learning environment of teaching through problem-solving provides a natural setting for students to present their solutions to their group or class in a way that is comfortable to them and learn mathematics through social interactions, meaning negotiation, and reaching a shared understanding (Lester Charles, 2003; Schoen Charles, 2003).

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating
Controlled Group			
Post-test	38	28.17	80.48 (Developing)
Experimental Group			
Post-test	38	29.97	85.62 (Approaching Proficiency)

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.37 with a p-value of .0371 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade four learners. This implies that the used of simplified worksheets in teaching mathematics four have contributed to the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of

the grade four learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Yavuz et al., (2015); Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development [OECD], 2014 (2017) who said that developing the ability of individuals to solve problems is one of the fundamental goals of education. Problem-solving is an essential competence in both education and daily life (Greiff et al., 2012). It is regarded as a complex cognitive activity that utilizes an individual's intellectual faculties (memory, perception, rea-

soning, conceptualization, and language) and appetitive faculties (emotions, motivation, and self-confidence; Raynal Rieunier, 1997). The problem-solving approach, also referred to as teaching through problem-solving, focuses on teaching mathematical topics through problem-solving contexts and inquiry-oriented environ-

ments, which are characterized by the teacher helping the students construct a deep understanding of mathematical ideas and processes by engaging them in doing mathematics: creating, conjecturing, exploring, testing, and verifying (Cai Lester, 2010).

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.37	.0371	Significant

Table 4 highlights the test of simplified worksheet approach on the mathematical skills of grade four learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.413 which signifies a large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in teaching mathematics subject which is essential for fostering numeracy, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking skills. The use of the problem-solving approach in teaching can facilitate the development and acquisition skills, knowledge, and expertise that are essen-

tial in the 21st-century society as it empowers students to develop critical thinking skills, foster a growth mindset, and acquire transferable skills that are essential for success in academic and real-life contexts. By engaging students in mathematical inquiry, exploration, and discovery, educators can cultivate a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, promote creativity and innovation, and instill a lifelong passion for learning mathematics (Fong et al., 2014; Dass, 2014).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 4 Learners

<i>N</i>	<i>t</i> -value	η^2	Descriptive Value	Decision
76	-4.34	0.413	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of simplified worksheets on the mathematical skills of grade four learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a superior design when the researcher

has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the

76 grade four learners – 38 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 38 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of simplified worksheets has increased the mathematical skills of grade four learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade learners in both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Limitations and Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Mathematics four should use role simplified worksheets as a strategy that would further develop the mathematical skills of grade four learners to make the teaching of mathematics meaningful. By engaging students in mathematical inquiry, exploration, and discovery, teachers can cultivate a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, promote creativity and innovation, and instill a lifelong passion for learning mathematics. The school heads should promote the use of simplified worksheet approach as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learn-

ing process as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that requires process of mathematical inquiry, exploration, and discovery. A school policy about the utilization of simplified worksheets approach can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using simplified worksheets approach as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of simplified worksheets approach as a strategy in teaching be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

4.3. Conclusions and Reflections—The findings indicate that utilizing simplified worksheets significantly enhances mathematical proficiency, as evidenced by the improved post-test scores of the experimental group compared to the control group. Despite limitations such as the non-random assignment of subjects, the study's results highlight the effectiveness of simplified worksheets in elevating students from the Beginning level to Approaching Proficiency. Consequently, it is recommended that Mathematics educators incorporate simplified worksheets to foster deeper mathematical understanding and enthusiasm for the subject. School administrators are encouraged to support this strategy by promoting its use and integrating it into school policies. Additionally, future research should explore further dimensions of this approach to solidify its benefits and identify new avenues for enhancing mathematical education. Through these measures, educators can create more engaging, effective, and innovative learning environments, ultimately bridging gaps in mathematical achievement and fostering a lifelong passion for learning among students.

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